

Assessing the Effect of Entrepreneurial Innovativeness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Innovation plays a crucial role in reinforcing the competitive advantage of firms. To be successful in a keenly competitive business environment, innovativeness is imperative and sine qua non to the marketing performance of the small business in particular. This study therefore assesses the effects of entrepreneurial innovativeness on marketing performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The research employed a descriptive survey research design. Using systematic and purposive sampling techniques, eight (8) local government areas (LGAs) in Ekiti state, Nigeria were selected for the study from which the sample were drawn. These LGAs were selected because they have the highest number of registered small businesses in the State. With the aid of proportionate sampling technique, 99, 35, 37, 29, 34, 62, 23 and 64 small businesses were selected from the eight previously selected LGAs respectively, totaling 383. Primary data used for the study were collected with the aid of semi-structured questionnaire. The analytical techniques employed for data analyses were means, standard deviation and multiple regression. Findings from the analysis revealed a significant and positive relationship between entrepreneurial innovativeness and marketing performance of small and medium enterprises especially in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study implied that the owners and managers of small and medium enterprises should improve on their innovative drive in order to be successful and remain competitive.

KEYWORDS: Innovativeness, Marketing Performance, Market Share, Customer Satisfaction, Entrepreneurship Innovation Theory, Small and Medium Enterprises

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have been generally acknowledged as the core and major drivers of many economies of the world's nations especially of developing nations like Nigeria. The role of small businesses in employment creation, provision of social security, entrepreneurship, poverty reduction, innovative thinking and indirect reduction in insecurity and crime rates by engaging idle hands cannot be overemphasized. Due to harsh economic condition and high rate of unemployment particularly among youth and mid-aged adults in Nigeria majority of these set of people have engaged themselves in one small and medium businesses or the other. Presently the small and medium enterprises sector is keenly competitive, to be successful therefore required the owners and managers of SMEs to be innovative and constantly introducing new products/service, creating new ideas, engaging in new production methods, opening of new markets and seeking new sources of supply. According to Aroyeun et al. (2019) innovative behaviour refers to an individual's actions directed towards introducing new and relevant ideas, principles, procedures, processes, and products (both goods and services). It involves a willingness to embrace new ideas that contribute to the creation and introduction of novel products. Innovation is key to the marketing performance of small business owners. Marketing performance according Usani et al. (2021) is the external efficacy measure for an organization. To Usani and Eko (2021), marketing performance is an economic measure of production efficiency in relation to customer retention, customer relationships, customer satisfaction, and the firm's increase in sales volume. Etuk et al. (2022) explained marketing performance based on four metrics of internal processes, customer, financial and innovativeness.

Though various studies (Mohammed, et al. 2018; Kimutai, 2018) on SMEs have been conducted, researchers seem to have ignored the possible effect of entrepreneurial innovativeness on marketing performance of SMEs especially in Ekiti State, Nigeria. As examples, Onikoyi, et al. (2021) studied effects of strategic management practices on organisational performance in Cadbury Nigeria plc with emphasis on determining effects of strategy formulation and implementation on organizational performance. Onyenma et al. (2020) conducted research examining the correlation between risk-taking and the performance of SMEs in Rivers and Bayelsa states of Nigeria. In Thailand, Meekaewkunchorn, et al. (2021) conducted a study on the mediating effects of learning orientation on the relationships between three dimensions (innovativeness, pro-activeness, and calculated risk-taking) of entrepreneurial

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orientation on SMEs' performance. None of the above studies have isolated entrepreneur's innovativeness and attempt to investigate its effects on the marketing performance of SMEs particularly in Ekiti State, Nigeria, hence this study.

This study therefore seeks to assess the effects of entrepreneur's innovativeness on the marketing performance of SMEs. Specifically, the study objective is to assess the effects of regular introduction of new products, emphasis on new innovation, increase in new equipment, changes in product or service line, continuous improvement and discovery of new ideas which are proxies of innovativeness on marketing performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Innovativeness

Introduction of new ideas, thoughts to produce a unique product or render an uncommon service to the people depict the innovative potentials in an organization. Innovative is one of the fundamental characteristics of an entrepreneur. It is the ability of an organization to create new idea, thought or build on existing ideas to gain competitive advantage in the business world (Oyeku, et al. 2020). For business organization to keep surviving in the business world, it requires an innovative potential to dance to the tune of the business environment.

According to Olanrewaju (2020), innovation is characterized by the willingness to deviate from existing systems, processes, or practices and to introduce or adopt new ideas or behaviors that are unfamiliar in the business world (Fred, 2019). It serves as a crucial factor driving SMEs' performance when a culture of innovation is applied strategically and systematically. Innovation is not only an organizational mindset but also a specific set of capabilities guiding innovative activities. In a similar vein, Helmy et al. (2020) defined innovation as the intentional generation, promotion, and realization of fresh ideas within a work role, workgroup, or organization by an employee, aiming to enhance role performance, the group, or the organization.

Aroyeun et al. (2019) suggested that innovative behaviour refers to an individual's actions directed towards introducing new and relevant ideas, principles, procedures, processes, and products (both goods and services). It also involves a willingness to embrace new ideas that contribute to the creation and introduction of novel products. Considering that innovation stems from innovativeness and innovation, in turn, encourages the development of new products and processes, potentially leading to heightened customer patronage and loyalty, it is logical to infer that innovativeness would have a positive correlation with the performance of firms.

Various scholars have conceptualized the term "innovation" in different ways. For instance, Fred (2019) defines innovation as the introduction of new products or alterations to existing ones, the adoption of new methods to reduce costs, the enhancement of a firm's system, recognizing the role of the market, and increasing productivity. Innovation is essentially the process of rejuvenating something that already exists or giving rise to something entirely new. From an entrepreneurial perspective, Jorg and Christopher (2020) articulate that innovation is closely tied to creativity. They further explain that innovation involves the successful implementation of an idea that not only adds value to the customer but also yields commercial returns for the creator. In Nigeria, numerous entrepreneurs actively engage in creating innovative products.

Innovation encompasses the initiation or introduction of novel products, services, or processes into the market through a specific business model, achieved either by utilization or commercialization. It entails any form of change or novelty, including the emulation of foreign or local products, the introduction of new production methods, or the utilization of new resources in production that can result in value creation in the market. Innovation plays a crucial role in bolstering the competitive advantage of firms. The innovation rate is a complex and multidimensional activity that cannot be directly measured with a single indicator. Therefore, a composite measure reflecting a firm's innovative capability is essential for assessing performance (Edamisan & Aarinola, 2019).

Each day, the business landscape undergoes continuous transformation due to the ever-evolving tastes and demands of consumers. Consequently, for small and medium enterprises to attain sustainability, it is imperative to enhance the frequency at which they introduce new products or services, or improve upon existing ones. Therefore, a higher rate of innovation directly correlates with increased performance for SMEs in the competitive business environment.

2.2 Marketing Performance

According to Jorg and Christoph (2020), performance is the ultimate result of assessing efforts made towards accomplishing predetermined goals and objectives. Adesanya et al. (2018) define performance as the anticipated outcome arising from a series of activities. Synthesizing these varied definitions, it becomes evident that performance is the consequence of a series of activities, reflecting the effective and efficient deployment of scarce resources to attain a desired goal. The combination of activities and resources yields an expected outcome, signifying the capability of a business venture to persist in the competitive business world. The performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) signifies the capacity of a small and medium-scale business enterprise to effectively harness the environment to streamline scarce and crucial resources for its operations (Hossain & Ahmed, 2019). Frequently, SMEs' performance is intertwined with its effectiveness and efficiency. As described by Olanrewaju (2020), organizational performance refers to the ability or proportional capacity of an organization to prudently employ the limited resources at its disposal to fulfill identified needs within its environment. Every SME, whether oriented towards production or services, is

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established to meet specific identified needs or desires while aiming for profitability. Therefore, the MSME's ability to fulfill the recognized needs of the public is denoted as organizational performance. Edamisan and Aarinola (2019) suggested that SMEs' performance encompasses their ability to effectively utilize available resources to meet established standards. The actual performance of SMEs can be categorized into financial and non-financial performance (Aroyeun, et al. 2019). Nevertheless, this study will specifically concentrate on non-financial performance.

Based on the above, marketing performance is explained as external efficacy measure for an organization (Usani et al., 2021). To Usani and Eko (2021), marketing performance is an economic measure of production efficiency in relation to customer retention, customer relationships, customer satisfaction, and the firm's increase in sales volume. Etuk et al. (2022) explained marketing performance using four major dimensions of internal processes, customer, financial and innovativeness.

Measuring marketing performance has recently attracted more attention from both researchers and industry professionals (Sampson et al., 2022; Etuk et al., 2022). Marketing performance allows marketers to assess the efficacy of their marketing efforts in relation to their plan's objectives. According to Etuk et al. (2022), marketing performance is the process of harmonising the marketing team's objectives with the tangible outcomes achieved. It is quantified by using measures such as revenues and sales volume, lead creation, customer retention, customer satisfaction, brand awareness, and customer engagement. Zufikar (2018) illustrates that the evaluation of marketing performance gauges the effectiveness of value creation, achieved through the enhancement of innovation skills and a comprehensive understanding of market orientation.

In this study marketing performance is the organisation's efforts aimed at converting the potential customers to realized customer and retaining such over a period of time through customer relationship and customer satisfaction with a view to maintaining or increasing the customer base and sales volume. It is the totality of the outcomes of the marketer or organization's efforts aimed at attracting new customers and retaining the existing ones with a view to increasing the organisation's customer base, sales volume and profit through quality products/services, customer satisfaction and customer relationship management. Simply put, marketing performance is the realisation of organisation's marketing objectives in the target market. It is measure in terms of market share and customer satisfaction.

2.2.1 Market Share

Market share denotes the percentage that a business holds within the total product purchases made by customers (Jorg & Christoph, 2020). This market share can be assessed based on either value or volume. Specifically, value market share is derived from a company's total share compared to overall segment sales, while volume market share pertains to the actual quantity of units sold by a business in relation to the total units sold in the market. When comparing these two metrics, the relationship between value and volume market share is not necessarily linear. In other words, a unit may have a high value but a low quantity, leading to a situation where the value market share is high while the volume market share is low.

Attaining a higher market share provides SMEs with a competitive edge. SMEs boasting substantial market shares benefit from advantageous cost prices negotiated with manufacturers due to their significant order volumes, thereby enhancing their purchasing influence (Olubiyi, et al., 2019). An increase in market share implies that, as the market expands, the leader secures a larger portion compared to others. Similarly, a market leader must stimulate market growth to fuel its own expansion. The term "market leader" denotes a product, brand, company, SMEs, organization, etc., holding the highest percentage of total sales. Strategies for augmenting market share involve initiatives like innovation, cultivating customer relationships (entrepreneurial orientation), implementing effective staffing practices, and outperforming competitors.

2.2.2 Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction is essentially the sense of contentment or fulfillment derived from a particular experience. Jorg and Christoph (2020) characterize satisfaction as an individual's emotional response, ranging from disappointment to pleasure, arising from a comparison between their perceptions of a product's performance and their initial expectations. Echoing this sentiment, Duru, et al. (2018) elaborate that customer satisfaction involves evaluating the difference between anticipated and perceived performance, assessing the alignment of purchase expectations with actual performance during the consumption of a product or service. Satisfaction is achieved when performance exceeds customer expectations, while dissatisfaction ensues if performance falls short of those expectations.

Customer satisfaction represents a positive emotional state resulting from an overall evaluation of the consumption experience (Olubiyi et al., 2019). It is the outcome of customers assessing how well their expectations align with their actual experience. In cases where the performance of a service surpasses customer expectations, it leads to positive confirmation, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction. Conversely, negative disconfirmation results in dissatisfaction. The concept of customer satisfaction is designed to enhance the long-term financial performance of businesses, positively influence customer loyalty, serve as a forward planner for future purchases, contribute to firms' profitability, enhance market value, and foster positive relationships within the cultural context (Hossain & Ahmed, 2019).

Satisfaction among customers with the products or services offered by SMEs is commonly perceived as a crucial factor contributing to a company's success and sustained competitiveness over the long term. The concept of customer satisfaction has evolved

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significantly as a fundamental construct in overseeing and managing activities within the relationship marketing paradigm. Oyeku, et al. (2020) assert that customer satisfaction is viewed as a transient emotional state arising from an individual comparison of a customer's expectations with the assessment of a specific product or service interaction.

2.3 Small and Medium Enterprises

Small and medium scale enterprise, small scale industries, and small-scale enterprises are used interchangeably to mean a small-scale industry firm. The criteria for classification of an enterprise as small, medium or large varies from one country to another, depending on whether it is a developed or developing country. A small business for example in one country may be a large-scale business in another. Hence, there is no universally accepted definition of small and medium enterprises as they are defined differently in accordance with the legislation of different countries. For instance, USAID in its definition of SMEs classified micro enterprise as informal businesses employing five or fewer workers including unpaid family labour; small enterprises as those operating in the formal sector with five to twenty employees; and medium enterprises as those employing 21 to 50 employees (Kayanula & Quartey in Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019).

The European Union (1995) explained SME as any enterprise employing less than 250 employees, and went further to break down the SME into micro (less than 10 employees, small (from 10 to 49 employees) and medium (between 50 to 249 employees). In Germany and Belgium, SMEs are establishments that employ at least 250 and 100 persons, in African countries, the average is around 200 and in Japan it is 300 (Etuk, et al. in Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019).

In Nigeria, the major criteria used in defining Small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) include number of employees, financial strength, sales value, initial capital outlay, relative size, independent ownership and the type of industry. In view of the above criteria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in its monetary policy circular No 22 of 1988 defined small-scale enterprises as having an annual turnover not exceeding five hundred thousand naira. While the Federal Ministry of Industries in 1973 defined small scale enterprises as businesses that have total capital (land, building machinery equipment and working capital) of up to ₦60, 000 and employ up to 50 persons (Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019). Also, the Central bank of Nigeria in its 1990 credit Guidelines for financial institutions characterized small-scale enterprises as those whose yearly turnover does not exceed ₦200 million or capital use does not exceed ₦200 million. In this study, small and medium enterprises are those businesses employing between 5 to 10 employees, with the working capital of ₦10-20 million and annual turnover or gross income of ₦15-25 million.

2.4 Empirical Review

Mohammed et al. (2018) investigated the impact of entrepreneurial innovativeness on the four types of firm performance. The study employed structural equation modeling partial least square (SEM-PLS) as method of analysis for the dataset of 450 SMEs in the wholesale and retail industry in Malaysia. The findings revealed that there was a significant positive impact of entrepreneurial innovativeness on three types of business performances namely perceived non-financial, perceived business growth and perceived performance relative to competitors. The reviewed study is delimited to entrepreneurial innovativeness while the current study will extend to calculated risk taking, pro-activeness, innovativeness and competitive aggressiveness.

Kimutai (2018) investigated the influence of entrepreneurial innovativeness on firm performance among small and medium-sized enterprises in Kenya (2006 – 2013). By using descriptive statistics, Pearson's bivariate correlation, multiple regression and moderated regression analysis, the study revealed that entrepreneurial innovativeness has a direct positive relationship with performance of mid-sized firms. The outcome of the study under review might not be tenable in Nigeria as a result in difference in economic system.

In Ghana, Ayepa, et al. (2019) examined the effects of innovativeness and firm resources on the growth of small enterprises in the Ga South Municipality. A sample of 188 registered small enterprises was selected from a population of 368 based on Krejcie and Morgan's 1970 Table. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study. Key findings from the hierarchy regression analysis is that innovativeness and firm resources have a positive but insignificant effect on the growth of small enterprises in the Ga South Municipality. The reviewed study was carried out in Ghana while the current study will be carried out in Nigeria.

Alyahyaei et al. (2020) investigated the impact of innovation on the business performance of SMEs in Oman. The research employed a quantitative approach in gathering and analysing data, using a self-administered questionnaire. PLS-SEM was the method of data analysis and revealed that innovation was positively and significantly related to business performance of SMEs in Oman. The reviewed study was limited to innovation as a predictor of SMEs performance while this present study would use calculated risk-taking, pro-activeness, innovativeness, competitiveness as predictors.

2.5 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Entrepreneurship Innovation Theory

The theory of entrepreneurship innovation propounded by Joseph Schumpeter (Pedersen, 2020) provides the basis for this study. Schumpeter identified five types of innovation: the introduction of new products, the introduction of new production methods, the

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opening of new markets, the establishment of new sources of supply, and the creation of new industry structures. He argued that entrepreneurs are innovators who disrupt the existing economic equilibrium through their introduction of new products, processes, or market approaches. Entrepreneurs who introduce these innovations contribute to economic growth and technological advancement. This theory emphasizes the importance of creative destruction, where entrepreneurial activities lead to the replacement of old technologies and practices with new and more efficient ones.

Due to its apparent bias and overemphasis on inventive functions, innovation theory is questioned. It disregards the purpose of taking risks, and Schumpeter's theories are especially relevant to developing nations where innovation needs to be promoted. The individual approach, with its single-cause logic, insensitivity to temporal dynamics, and failure to account for contextual factors, and the situational approach, with its emphasis on adaptation and ensuing failure to account for human agency, are among the other ways in which Schumpeter's theory has been criticized for failing to account for entrepreneurial action on a micro level (Gartner, 2001; Thornton, 1999; Shaver & Scott, 1992). This theory is relevant to this study because the theory states that when the economy is in distress, profit motivated entrepreneurs will innovate, create and invent new things, products and services to stimulate productivity and job creation, thereby increasing wealth and profit just as it's being witness in Nigeria in recent time due to turbulent business environment occasioned by unfriendly government policies.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research employed a descriptive survey research design. Using systematic and purposive sampling techniques, eight (8) local government areas (LGAs) out of the sixteen LGAs in Ekiti state, Nigeria were selected for the study. The LGAs are Ado, Ekiti East, Ekiti West, Gbonyin, Ijero, Ikole, Irepodun/Ifelodun and Moba from which the sample were drawn. These LGAs were selected because they have the highest number of registered small businesses in the State. With the aid of proportionate sampling technique, 99, 35, 37, 29, 34, 62, 23 and 64 small businesses were selected from the eight previously selected LGAs respectively, totaling 383. Primary data used for the study were collected with the aid of semi-structured questionnaire and analysed using means, standard deviation and multiple regression.

3.1 Model Specification

To achieve the objective, multiple regression was employed and the model is developed as follows:

$$PER = f(INV) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$INV = f(RINP, ENI, INE, CPS, TNII, ECI, DNI) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where:

PER = Performance

INV = Innovativeness

RINP = Regular Introduction of New Products

ENI = Emphasis on New Innovation

INE = Increase in New Equipment

CPS = Change in Product Services

TNII = Test of New Ideas Internationally

ECI = Emphasis on Continuous Improvement

DNI = Discussion of New Ideas

The multiple regression model was further developed as:

$$PER = \alpha + \beta_1RINP + \beta_2ENI + \beta_3INE + \beta_4CPS + \beta_5TNII + \beta_6ECI + \beta_7DNI + \mu \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where:

PER = Performance (Dependent Variable)

RINP = Regular Introduction of New Products

ENI = Emphasis on New Innovation

INE = Increase in New Equipment

CPS = Changes in Product or Service line

TNII = Testing of New Ideas Internationally

ECI = Emphasis on Continuous Improvement

DNI = Discovery of New Ideas

α = Constant

μ = Stochastic Error Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_7$ = Gradient of the Slope

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4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondents Perception on Innovativeness on SMEs Performance (n=163)

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Our business regularly introduces new products	4.43	0.745	Agree
2	Our business places a strong emphasis on innovative equipment	4.17	0.772	Agree
3	Our business has increased the number of new product during the past two years	4.07	0.959	Agree
4	Over the past few years, changes in our services or product lines have been quite dramatic	3.93	1.013	Agree
5	Our firm continuously tests new ideas in the neighboring towns	4.13	0.917	Agree
6	Our business places strong emphasis on continuous improvement in our procedures	4.15	0.964	Agree
7	Our top management openly discusses new ideas with the employees	4.06	0.967	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.13	0.905	Agree

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Moreover, Table 1 presented the respondents' reactions to the statements in the research instrument. The mean responses for all statements consistently exceeded 3.0, resulting in the decision recorded in the last column of the table. The analysis from the table indicates a strong affirmation from the respondents regarding the impact of innovativeness on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The participants concurred that innovativeness significantly contributed to the success of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in their respective businesses. Additionally, the respondents agreed that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises regularly introduce new products. The overall assessment of the function of innovativeness yielded a grand mean of 4.13.

4.1 Hypothesis Testing

Ho: Innovativeness has no significant effect on the performance of small and medium scale enterprise in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 2. Innovativeness and Micro Small and Medium Scale Enterprise Performance

Model	R	R ²	Adj R ²	B	Std Error	T value	P Value
	.687	.545	.541				
Innovativeness				.641	.070	4.556	.000
Constant				1.332	.292	9.208	.000
		F cal = 84.796		F tab = 1.960			

Source: Data Analysis (2023)

The hypothesis of the study focuses on innovativeness and its effects on performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria was tested using multiple regression analysis. As presented in Table 2 the regression coefficient between small and medium-scale enterprise performance and the explanatory variable (innovativeness) exhibited a positive value of 0.681. This indicates that innovativeness has a strong positive effect on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, suggesting a positive impact of the explanatory variable on performance. The coefficient of multiple determination (R²), standing at 0.545, signifies that the explanatory variable (innovativeness) can account for 54.5% of the variation in small and medium-scale enterprise performance. The remaining 45.5% of the variation can be attributed to stochastic variables or other factors not considered in the study.

The adjusted R² further supports these findings, registering a coefficient of 0.541. This adjusted value indicates that after accounting for adjustments, the explanatory variable (innovativeness) explains 54.1% of the variability in small and medium-scale enterprise performance. The remaining 45.9% is attributed to the error term or other unconsidered variables.

From Table 2 the unstandardized β coefficient of innovativeness yields a positive value of 0.641 with $t=4.556$ and $(P=0.000 < 0.05)$. This result indicates a highly significant effect of innovativeness on the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, establishing its statistical significance. The positive relationship between innovativeness and small and medium-scale enterprise performance suggests that respondents' rationale for performance is strongly and positively influenced by their innovative practices, as shown in Table 4.9. A higher T-value enhances the result, and the positive nature of the result signifies a positive association between innovativeness and the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. This is likely due to small and medium-scale enterprise owners or managers regularly introducing new products through innovative equipment, testing new ideas in neighboring towns, emphasizing continuous procedure improvement, and openly discussing new ideas with employees.

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The F-test is employed to assess the overall significance of the model by comparing the calculated F-value with the tabulated F-value, as outlined in Table 4.9. The table indicates that the calculated F-value exceeds the tabulated F-value. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that innovativeness significantly affects the performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

This finding aligns with the research conducted by Oman, Alyahyaei, Husin, and Supia (2020), who examined the impact of innovation on the business performance of SMEs in Oman using PLS-SEM as the method of data analysis. The study revealed that innovation was positively and significantly related to the business performance of SMEs in Oman. Additionally, Mohmmed, Shehnaz, and Constance Van (2018) found a significant positive impact of entrepreneurial innovativeness on three types of business performances, namely perceived non-financial, perceived business growth, and perceived performance relative to competitors. They analyzed the impact of entrepreneurial innovativeness on the four types of firm performance in Malaysia.

Therefore, the regression line is stated below:

$$\text{SMEs Performance} = 1.332 + 0.641\text{Inn}$$

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The effects of innovativeness on the performance of small and medium enterprises was investigated using multiple regression analysis. The results indicated that innovativeness holds significant importance in relation to the performance of small and medium enterprises leading to the acceptance of the alternate hypothesis and the rejection of the null hypothesis. The findings demonstrated that innovativeness is both significant and positively correlated with the performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

This discovery aligns with the research conducted by Mohammed, et al. (2017), which highlighted that innovation significantly affects the performance of SMEs in Hargeisa. Similarly, in the study by Etim, et al. (2017), it was revealed that innovation is a critical element of entrepreneurial orientation influencing the survival of SMEs in Nigeria. Gilbert (2018) also reported that entrepreneurial innovativeness has a direct positive relationship with the performance of mid-sized firms. In contrast, Ayepa, et al. (2019) concluded that innovativeness does not significantly influence the resources and growth of small enterprises.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings, the study concludes that increase in entrepreneurial innovativeness led to a significant and positive improvement in marketing performance of small businesses generally. The study highlighted the imperativeness of continuous innovation to the marketing success of small and medium enterprises. Sequel to this, small business owners need to engage in continuous introduction of new products, emphasis should be on new inventions and increase in new equipment if they are to be successful in a very keenly competitive business environment. It is expedient to emphasise that marketing performance of small businesses depends largely on discovering new ideas, testing new ideas internationally and changes to their product or service lines when necessary. Emphasis on continuous improvement in processes, methods and procedures of doing things and searching and access to market information is *sin-qua-non* to success.

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